

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CERTAIN LEGAL ASPECTS RELATING TO TIME-CHARTER PARTIES AND THE OBLIGATIONS OF SHIPOWNERS AND CHARTERERS UNDER ENGLISH LAW

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Abstract

"Time charter" is a contract for vessel hire where the ship owner or the bareboat charterer, in the case of a previous bareboat charter, rents out the vessel with a crew. Responsibility for a vessel is with the ship owner or bareboat charterer, who is also responsible for the cargo. Time charterers use the vessel to carry their own or other charterers cargoes against payment of freight by concluding the relevant voyage charter. The time charterer is responsible for the execution of the voyage charter, but in general, the responsibility for the cargo remains with the shipowner, who may be the actual shipowner or the bareboat charterer. According to English private maritime law, it is permissible in a time charter to agree that responsibility for the cargo passes to the time charterer, and for this reason, the time charterer's name appears on the bill of lading as a carrier.

Keywords: Time-charter under English Law; Period Time-Charter; Trip Time-Charter; Shipowners obligations; Charterers obligations; Bill of Lading Carrier

1. Introduction to the Time Charter under English Maritime Private Law

Contracts for letting a ship on hire with an appointed crew by ship owners are known as time charters. Specifically, the owners of ships under time charter control their vessels but do not exploit them commercially. The time charterer exploits the vessel commercially under their time charter for the specified duration. The technical maintenance of a vessel on a time charter remains the owner's responsibility. Shipowners employ and direct the crew on board the vessel. A shipowner can be either the registered shipowner or the bareboat charterer if the ship is on a bareboat charter. Registered ship owners, who appoint the crew on board, are the legal owners of the ship. In this case, legal shipowners secure their possession through the master and crew of the vessel, who are their servants. If the vessel is on a bareboat charter, the bareboat charterers receive the right to possess the vessel, and based on this, they appoint the crew for the duration of the charter. The shipowner transfers the use of the vessel, also known as the "right to use," to the time charterer. This means that in exchange for paying rent, the charterers receive the right to use the vessel for their commercial activities, such as carrying their cargoes, arranging voyage charters for the carriage of other charterer cargoes, or subletting the ship to other charterers under a time charter. In time charters, the shipowner remains responsible for the technical maintenance and management of the ship and is obliged to transfer to the time charterer the commercial operation of the vessel - "*the right to exploit the earning capacity of the vessel*" [1] (right for benefit from the possibilities for income from the ship). In these contracts, the costs for loading and

unloading the ship also pass from the shipowner to the time charterer. When a ship on time charter carries another charterer's cargo, then the time charterer is in the capacity of a carrier (disponent owner) who has concluded a voyage charter with shippers. In these contractual relations, the time charterer is a carrier by charter (disponent owner) and is responsible to the shipper for transporting the commodity on a liner or under net conditions as per the governing liner bill of lading or voyage charter. So, in these cases, the agreement for the carriage is between the time charterer, who is acting as a carrier, and the shipper. Also, in these cases, vessel fixed costs (daily running costs and capital costs) are for the account of the shipowner, and the variable (voyage) expenses of the ship are for the account of the time charterer. The time charterer pays for variable (voyage) costs of the ship, as the fuel and the disbursement accounts. Time charterers negotiate with shippers the conditions for the carriage of the cargo, including the freight, loading, and unloading. On the other hand, time charterers remain obligated to shipowners for loading and discharge of cargo and payment of vessel hire as per the time charter. Registered ship owners ensure time-chartered vessels for H&M and P&I, but in the case of a previous bareboat charter, bareboat charterers bear the insurance costs. Registered ship owners, or bareboat charterers, are responsible for ensuring vessel compliance with the ISM Code. The main responsibility of ship owners to time charterers is to maintain the vessel to be seaworthy, also satisfactory performance concerning speed and fuel consumption.

The party that rents a vessel for a specific period has the right to transport its own goods on the vessel.

Under those circumstances, any bill of lading that is issued serves as a receipt and document of title, primarily fulfilling that purpose. However, its terms typically do not establish the terms of the contract of carriage, which would be established by the governing time charter party.

It is possible that the charterer, after chartering the ship, may frequently offer it to other shippers. These shippers typically demand a receipt and a document of title to facilitate sales. This is accomplished through the issuance of a bill of lading, which can typically be requested from the carrier under the Hague and Hague-Visby Rules. The bill of lading serves as proof of, or forms a contractual agreement for, the transportation of goods. It can be transferred as a document that establishes the contract of carriage with the party responsible for shipping the goods, whether it is the owner or the charterer. Occasionally, third-party shippers may be unaware that the ship is under time charter. In other cases, they may be aware of this fact, such as when the bill of lading mentions a charter party. However, even if they are aware, they may not necessarily know the specific terms of the time charter party or be able to identify the specific charter party in question.

Ultimately, even if the person who charters the ship does so themselves, they will probably want the ability to transfer the cargo either in its entirety or in parts. When the bill of lading, which initially serves as a receipt and proof of ownership, is transferred, the recipient will obtain a document that not only serves these functions but also functions as the agreement for transporting the goods (which was previously the charter party) and is typically transferable in this manner.

The main issue in a time charter is the responsibility for the cargo, or who shall be responsible for the cargo as per the bill of lading. According to the bill of lading, the carrier is responsible for the cargo. The question then arises: *how shall it be determined who is the carrier as per the bill of lading?*"

2. General rights and responsibilities of a Time Charter

In time charter contracts, the shipowner is responsible for the crew and technical maintenance. The time charterer, in exchange for the rent they pay, obtains the right to use the ship for transporting their own and other charterers' cargoes at their own expense, effectively gaining operational control of the vessel. The time charterer transports other charterers' cargoes at their own expense by arranging voyage charters or issuing liner bills of lading, thereby assuming the role of a charter carrier.

The designation of the bill of lading carrier for goods transported under the voyage charter or liner bill of lading is agreed upon in the time charter between the shipowner and the time charterer. If the time charter specifies that the time charterer is to be the carrier of the bills of lading, this agreement is recorded on the second page of the bill of lading, in the free field at the top right corner.

If the time charter stipulates that the shipowners are to be the carriers of the bills of lading, it is not necessary for the bill of lading to reflect this agreement. In cases where the carrier's name is not written on the bill

of lading, the shipowner, according to the ship's Certificate of Registration, is considered the carrier. The Certificate of Registration for the ship is issued in the name of the ship owner.

When the vessel is under a bareboat charter, a temporary certificate of registration for the vessel is issued in the name of the bareboat charterer. [2]

3. Duration of the Time Charter

The negotiated duration of charters is calculated in two ways:

- For a certain period (fixed time/term) – Period Charterers

Coghlin, T., (2014), I.16. *The charter party typically determines the duration of each type of time charter to distinguish between them. The charter may provide that the vessel will be chartered for a specified period specified in the charter, whether short or long, fixed or variable, for example, "6 months," or "from 6 to 9 months," or "6 months and 15 days more or less." Such charters are called time charters, or period charters for short, and the charterers can direct the ship to undertake as many individual voyages within the agreed-upon period as they wish.*[3]

- Duration equal to the duration of one transport - Trip Charterer

Coghlin, T., (2014), I.17. *On the other hand, a charter may define its period and limit the services to be taken on a particular voyage or "flight" (or on several specified voyages). Such a charter is called a "voyage time charter," and the service (or any service) to be performed is a "charter voyage." Although, as with any other time charter, the owners' remuneration will be a periodic (usually daily) charter, a voyage time charter may, in other respects, have more in common with a voyage than, for example, a long-term charter transaction in world trade, which carries all kinds of cargo. Whether all the usual time charter cases apply to a time charter for a fixed or narrowly defined voyage is not fully explored in the cases. However, a mistake can be made if such a time charter is seen as something like a charter flight. See, for example, the Court of Appeal's criticism of certain aspects of the decision at first instance in *The Doric Pride* [2006] 2 Lloyd's Rep. 175, per Rix, L.J., at pages 178 and 179, although it did not affect the result in this case. For a recent decision by Teare, J., on whether the text is for a voyage charter or a time charter with the duration of the voyage, see *The Sabrina 1* (2011) LMLN 814. [3]*

A lot of charterers prefer for the carriage of their goods to hire time-charter vessels, based on a certain trip limited between two or more ports within the voyage, also sometimes for a round trip. These charters acquired fame such as "trip-charter" and "round trip-charter". A trip charter is like a voyage charter about the duration of the flight and the intention to transport some kind in advance the specified quantity of commodity, per one or a few trips between relevant ports. The similarities are limited only in this, but creature charterers and shipowners undertake the obligations entirely inherent in the usual one-time charter for continuous periods.[3]

4. Other perspectives on the Time Charter

If a particular ship is chartered for a specified period – for example, 12 months with an option of an additional 15 days more or less – then the responsibilities of the parties will differ significantly from those in voyage time charters. Under a time-charter, the time charterer assumes control of the commercial operation and use of the ship, bearing expenses related to commercial operation such as payments to ship agents for disbursement bills and fuel costs, while the shipowner retains responsibility for ship maintenance, crew hiring, insurances, etc., i.e., fixed costs. In exchange for granting the ship under charter, the shipowner receives rent, typically prepaid for a whole or half month. In cases where the ship is unable to be utilized due to circumstances beyond the shipowner's control – for example, accidents – for which the charterer is not responsible, the period is considered off-hire, and during this time, the shipowner does not receive rent.

5. Some aspects of BIMCO Time Charter forms GENTIME and NYPE

"Thomas, D. (2014) describes the General Time Charter (GENTIME) contract as a charter agreement that differs from the New York Produce Exchange (NYPE) contract in several aspects. It stipulates a specific period or number of trips, optional time intervals, and includes a buffer period at the end. Moreover, the GENTIME contract incorporates an interpellation provision, enabling owners to notify charterers earlier if they cannot meet the cancellation date.

An additional sub-clause has been added to GENTIME, clarifying that the Charterers' acceptance of the vessel does not undermine or affect any rights they may have against the Owners. This clause serves as a cautionary notice to Charterers regarding the commencement of hire payments.

Furthermore, the GENTIME contract specifies geographical regions where the ship's trading takes place. An additional sub-clause obligates to guarantee that the vessel has not previously traded in regions that could potentially limit its future operations. This clause serves as a cautionary notice to Charterers regarding the possibility of the vessel being subjected to a boycott in specific regions.

Regarding cargo, GENTIME explicitly states that hazardous cargo can only be transported with the consent of the owners and permits the transportation of radioisotopes under specific circumstances. Additionally, it provides provisions for containers, which must adhere to the regulations outlined in the International Convention for Safe Containers. Clauses 17 and 18 cover the transportation of deck cargo, while clause 13 addresses both the handling of deck cargo and the amount of space on the vessel accessible to the charterers.

Redelivery is another important aspect of the GENTIME contract, requiring Charterers to provide notice of the expected date and place of redelivery. Sub-clause 4(b) specifies the predetermined location or range of ports for the vessel's redelivery. This clause clarifies that the owners' acceptance of redelivery does not affect any rights they may have against the Charterer.

Furthermore, the GENTIME contract emphasizes the obligation to adhere to the law and national regulations, as well as the necessity of carrying the appropriate certificates on board to demonstrate compliance with these regulations. Clause 7(c) stipulates that the vessel must have Suez and Panama fittings on board, a requirement not addressed in the NYPE agreement.

The GENTIME charter party agreement incorporates terms regarding the rate of hiring and payment in a single clause, which is essentially identical to the provisions found in NYPE. However, the anti-technicality provision allows for delays in payment of hire if Charterers or their bank make errors or omissions.

The off-hire clause in the GENTIME charter party explicitly specifies the circumstances under which the vessel is considered off-hire. Deviation and requisition are both encompassed within the same clause, and the rate of hire for this additional period will be the rate in effect upon returning the item.

In conclusion, the GENTIME contract offers a more comprehensive and detailed approach to vessel charter agreements than the NYPE agreement.

The General Terms of Reference (GENTIME) is a comprehensive agreement for the carriage of goods and services on board a vessel. It includes several clauses that outline the responsibilities and duties of the Charterers, Owners, and Master. The Master's supervision is crucial in ensuring the vessel's seaworthiness and safeguarding the Owners and Master from any demands made by Charterers that could pose a threat to the vessel or the environment.

Bills of Lading are also included in GENTIME, allowing Charterers to issue through bills and multimodal bills. However, if the Owners' responsibility extends beyond the duration of the cargo being on board the vessel, the Charterers will be required to compensate the Owners for any claims arising from loss, damage, or expenses. A clause has been included that forbids the use of bills that include the Hamburg Rules, unless they are mandatory, or any other rules that increase the liabilities of owners beyond what is necessary according to the Hague/Hague-Visby Rules.

In conclusion, GENTIME is a comprehensive agreement that addresses the responsibilities and obligations of both Charterers and Owners in the transportation of goods and services. [4]

6. Shipowner' Obligations as per BIMCO forms GENTIME and NYPE

Thomas, D. (2014) This clause stipulates the crucial responsibility of delivering a vessel that meets the standards of Class and is in fully operational condition, both in terms of its hull and machinery. It also requires the charterer to ensure that the vessel remains in such Class and is continuously maintained to be suitable for service throughout the duration of the charter agreement. In the New York Produce Exchange (NYPE) agreement, this obligation is discreetly included in Clause 6, which enumerates the items that the Owners are responsible for providing and covering the costs of.

GENTIME asserts that the Owners are always accountable for the navigation of the vessel and the provision of associated services, such as pilotage and tow-

age, even if these expenses are covered by the Charterers. The clause comprehensively enumerates all the items that NYPE specifies in its Clauses 6 (Owners to provide), Documentation. In addition, GENTIME includes Crew Assistance for various operations and a sub-clause regarding deratisation. [4]

7. Time Charterers Obligations as per BIMCO forms GENTIME and NYPE

Thomas, D. (2014) The clause specifies that the Charterers have a duty to maintain and safeguard the cargo during loading and unloading at ports, as well as take responsibility for stevedoring operations, arranging transshipment, and ensuring proper delivery of the cargo.

Clause 7 in NYPE, titled "Charterers to Provide," is a unique combination of items that may be paid for by either the Charterers or the Owners, depending on the circumstances. The GENTIME document explicitly enumerates all the items that the Charterers are responsible for providing and covering the costs of. The mentioned costs in the second part of Clause 8 of NYPE pertain to cargo handling expenses. Instances that could be attributed to either the Owners or the Charterers have been incorporated into a distinct Clause 16 (Sundry Matters).[4]

8. Signing Bill of Lading and Carrier's Identification

The identification of the carrier on a chartered vessel can be challenging, especially when the bill of lading is in the hands of a shipper or receiver who is not a party to the governing charter party. This can lead to confusion in the contract of carriage between the shipowner and the charterer, as well as between the cargo interest and the 'carrier' as stated on the bill of lading. In most cases, the 'carrier' could be either the shipowner, the time-charterer, or even a sub-charterer. Determining whether to pursue an action against the time charterer or the shipowner is crucial for a cargo claimant, as pursuing the wrong party or disregarding the advantage of suing multiple parties could waste time and expense.

Pejovic, C., (2000), In English law, the shipowner bears liability as the carrier when the master or the charterer signs the bill of lading. The master usually has the authority to enter contracts on behalf of the shipowner by signing the bill of lading as his agent. However, the charterer has no general authority to sign a bill of lading on behalf of the shipowner. In the case of time charters, the shipowner's liability for cargo-related claims stems from the charterer's deemed signature on the bill of lading. The English courts consider the identity of the carrier to be a matter of fact that depends on the circumstances. Thus, the master may bind the charterer rather than the shipowner if the terms of the charter party or bill of lading, together with other circumstances, indicate that the master is acting as the charterer's agent.

Identity of the carrier clauses have been recognized by the English courts to reduce uncertainty, but where the bill of lading clearly identifies the charterer as the carrier, the effect of such clauses is doubtful. [5]

Coghlin, T., Kimbal, J., Baker, A., Belnap, Jr. T., Kenny, J., (2014), According to Clause 8 of the New York Produce form, the master is required to sign bills of lading "as presented." This means that the bills of lading are given to the master by the charterers or their agents for him to sign. This provision has a wide-ranging impact in a time charter, but it does not mean that the charterers have the right to compel the captain to sign any bill of lading, regardless of its contents or terms of carriage (which determine the relationship between the shipowners and the bill holder). Nevertheless, the courts have not yet provided a comprehensive definition of the situations in which the captain of a ship under a time charter can refuse to sign bills of lading, as well as the repercussions of the captain signing bills of lading that he could have legally declined to sign.[4]

Conclusion:

- Legal features: Under the time charter, the ship remains in the possession of the shipowner, which broadly encompasses the terms ship owner or ship possessor (Bareboat charterer). The time charterer functions as a user who utilizes the earning capacity of the ship against the paid rent.

- Organizational features: The time charter allows for the transportation of its cargo or functions as a carrier (disponent owner) to transport other charterers' cargoes in liner and tramp shipping, against freight received, or to sublease the ship to a sub-charterer against sub-hire.

- Liability for cargo: The question of liability is more complex. Cargo liability is typically negotiated and allocated between the ship owner and the time charterer through special clauses and agreements, such as the Interclub agreement.

- Application: These contracts are utilized by charterers (shippers and speculators) who transport their own and other charter's cargoes on time or tramp terms at their own expense.

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